

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article is aimed at studying the impact of an international language, which is becoming popular nowadays, on the knowledge of the English language. The article also focuses on the study of vocabulary and language skills: speaking, reading and writing, and we consider the effect of several elements of social media on each. From the results of this study, we can safely say that social media has more influence on our writing skills than any other skills. Advanced software can turn any large message into a simple game. The reason is that our smartphones have become smarter than our spoken conversation. For example, the basic building blocks of any language lie in its roots and sentence structures. Similar conversational processes are replaced or modified on smartphones by introducing several elements such as abbreviations, emoticons, and auto-completion. This article examines the positive and negative aspects of the influence of the media on the language and makes a critical assessment.

Key words: linguistics, social media, text, emoji, facebook, sociology.

INTRODUCTION. A person is socially active, and the main part of his life is realized as a result of interaction and communication with other people. Social life can arise and develop only if people are connected to each other, which encourages them to interact and transmit information through various communication channels. That is, in turn, social communication is the behavior of people in society, directed to others in order to expect a corresponding reaction in response. Social communication includes:

- 1) communication subjects (from two to several people);
- 2) subject of communication (reason for communication);
- 3) "I" (person) is a mechanism for regulating relations¹⁸⁴.

Communication is a unique form of realizing social relations between people, their mutual relations as members of society. The social meaning of communication lies in the transmission of cultural forms and social experience accumulated by mankind over many years. Communication is one of the means of forming a person as a person. A person's behavior, activity, attitude to the world and to himself are largely

¹⁸⁴ Цветкова Л. С. Нейропсихологическая реабилитация. Речь и интеллектуальная деятельность. М.:Издательство Московского университета, 2001.

determined by his communication with other people. Communication has three interrelated aspects.

1) communicative side - consists of information exchange and transmission by people;

2) interactive side - organization of interactions between people;

3) perceptual side - establishment of mutual understanding based on mutual perception of communication partners and personal attitude towards each other¹⁸⁵. The main components of communication are purpose, medium and content. That is, why people communicate, how people communicate (methods of communicating information), and what people communicate about (information communicated).

Language is one of the rare gifts of nature that can make or break a people, society or nation. Language as a means of communication is systematically coded¹⁸⁶. Phonemes (speech sounds) are conditionally divided into orthographic images and segments of the spelling system. English, like other developed human languages, has semiotic symbols and spelling systems that are used in all forms of written communication. Anyone who is a first, second, or foreign user of English (who can know it) knows the semiotic conventions of the language and can linguistically recognize and use them in any normal medium and context. Social media (or more precisely, networking) is one of the channels where language is used strongly.

Social Media Web-based communication tools include a variety of electronic or mediated technology channels that facilitate communication and interaction between individuals and groups in cyberspace. Unlike human language, which is structurally and grammatically conditional, social media use various forms of networks specific to users or groups to communicate locally among such groups or customers.

Today, communication processes have become much simpler and have moved to social media. Nowadays, almost all people communicate through social networks. In relational terms, there is debate about the intimacy and quality of online relationships in Internet settings.

Social networks are very popular and influential among today's youth. Previous media theories, including Uses and Gratifications, Cultivation Analysis, and Media Ecology Theory, have proposed ways in which media can be used and influenced. The rise of social media poses new challenges to existing behavioral and media theories. Media has changed dramatically in the past decade. Traditional media such as television and radio present content in one direction, distributing content created by a company or corporation to be consumed by a passive audience. Alternatively, new media – often referred to as social media or interactive media – provide unlimited opportunities for users to act as both consumers and creators of media.

¹⁸⁵ Широкова Е. А. Практика преподавания иностранных языков на факультете международных отношений БГУ: сборник / Е. А. Широкова. – Вып. II, 2012

¹⁸⁶ Nwala, M. A. (2015). Introduction to linguistics: A first course. (rev. edition Port Harcourt: Obisco Nig. Enterprises.)

Examples of social media interactivity include posting a new photo on Instagram, commenting on a YouTube video, or "downvoting" content on Reddit. New media are digital, often manipulable, networkable, dense, compressible, and interactive¹⁸⁷. The emergence of new, digital technologies "signals a potentially fundamental shift in who controls information, expertise, and resources"¹⁸⁸. In the context of these dramatic changes and rapid developments, this chapter examines social media and health behavior theory.

With the transition to web applications, the media industry has experienced a major paradigm shift in both media production and circulation: "Using these new technologies, audiences occupying a place at the intersection of new and old media are demanding the right to participate. The result of the desire to participate is the opportunity for ordinary people to create and distribute media content themselves, opening the door to different opinions and perspectives or user-generated content. Today we need to conceptualize areas to understand the dynamics of online participation where traditional media theory aligns with new media practices.

METHODS. First of all, it is necessary to answer the question of what is social media. Social media is a collection of software and web tools that help users communicate online, share content, and develop a personalized network of friends, colleagues, or organizations. Each individual uses their network differently, and there are no hard and fast rules about what is "right" for each site. Users come to social networking sites to chat with friends, share ideas, and hear the latest news. They generally don't go to their inbox looking to buy something, but instead to see news about friends or relatives or read the latest news happening in the world. Even on business-oriented sites like LinkedIn, direct marketing messages should be done infrequently and with caution. The main purpose of any sites is definitely financial gain. That's why it's a good idea to consider these sites' social media ads in more ways than just "Buy this product." For example:

- Write an article about your work and post a link to it in relevant groups and forums; Don't forget to add a note about your product.
- Join groups related to your work and follow the comments of other users. Is someone asking a question that you can answer? Then answer it and put a link on your homepage or blog or anywhere your book can be found.
- Is there anything in the news about your work? Make sure your friends and colleagues know! In short, social media works best if you participate and support the communities you join. If you want to learn more about social media, there are tons of books, blogs, and websites that are easy to find with a quick search on Google or your favorite search engine. Once you get started, you'll find that it's not difficult, although it does require some dedication and

¹⁸⁷Terry Flew & Richard Smith ARTICLE/CHAPTER TITLE: Mobile New Media JOURNAL/BOOK TITLE: New Media: An Introduction VOLUME: DATE: 2011 . P. 279-289

¹⁸⁸An experimental method for studying unconscious perception in a marketing context Stewart Shapiro, Deborah J. MacInnis, Susan E. Heckler, Ann M. Perez 1999, [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1520-6793\(199909\)16:6<459::AID-MAR2>3.0.CO;2-2](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1520-6793(199909)16:6<459::AID-MAR2>3.0.CO;2-2)

patience. The impact of social media on the English language Over the centuries, the English language has developed under the influence of literature, theater, film, the press, technology, and another reason is new ways of communication. Social networks are the main driving force of changes, connections, shifts and maintenance of language functions¹⁸⁹. In sociolinguistics and empirical studies of social networks, the interaction of personal qualities of network communicators in the practical implementation of social networks and language tools is analyzed in detail¹⁹⁰. Social media seems to be the first medium of communication that puts the writer in a certain circle. Facebook is almost the first site connection or the starting point of every young person's social network communication; That is why the number of people (especially young people) who enter the Facebook social network every day is thousands of millions. The Facebook network is full of new and unconventional linguistic writing styles. This is because the web is user-friendly, open and linguistically user-specific. It is an American online social network. It is an online site that allows registered users to create individual or group profiles, upload photos, videos and messages, find friends, meet different people and make new friends. Facebook was created on February 4, 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg. Since its evolution, social media has witnessed tremendous interest, especially since the site can be accessed through a wide range of connections such as desktop computers, laptops and smartphones. Facebook is almost the first site connection or the starting point of every young person's social network communication; That is why the number of people (especially young people) who enter the Facebook social network every day is thousands of millions. The Facebook network is full of new and unconventional linguistic writing styles. This is because the web is user-friendly, open and linguistically user-specific. Today, people have become accustomed to spending time on social networks and doing all their tasks online. For example, trade, business, education, logistics, culture, show business, and all other fields are making good use of social networks. In some ways, this will stimulate positive changes and development. According to the results of January 2023, the most used social network in Uzbekistan was recognized as Telegram, but we have collected the number of users of developed social networks in the world and give it as a source.

¹⁸⁹ Labov, William. 2001. Principles of Linguistic Change (II): social factors. Oxford, UK: Blackwell.

¹⁹⁰ Milroy, Lesley. 1980/1987. Language and Social Networks. Oxford: B. Blackwell.

SOCIAL MEDIA STATISTICS FOR UZBEKISTAN IN 2023 THERE WERE 6.25 MILLION SOCIAL MEDIA USERS IN UZBEKISTAN IN JANUARY 2023

Pic. 1. Social media users in 2023 in January for Uzbekistan

It is worth noting that Telegram is considered the most used and safe social network because total audience of Telegram channels comprises 740,990,000 people¹⁹¹ in Uzbekistan. Kaplan and Haenlein identified six classifications for social media platforms related to their function. Collaborative projects (Wikipedia), Blogs and microblog sites (Twitter, Tumblr), Social networking sites (Telegram, Facebook), Content communities (YouTube, Pinterest, Instagram, Vine), Virtual game-worlds (World of Warcraft), Virtual social worlds (Second Life)¹⁹². It is clear from this that humanity cannot imagine its life without social networks. And this certainly does not affect the language and especially affects our written language.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS. The concept of the linguistic representation of the world in social networks goes back to the ideas of Wilhelm von Humboldt and neo-Humboldtists about the internal form of language. Humboldt was one of the first linguists who paid attention to the national content of language and thought and noted that "different languages are for a nation their original organs of thought and perception." Each person has a subjective image of the same object that does not completely correspond to the image of another person. So, the word carries the burden of subjective ideas, their differences are within certain limits, because their carriers are members of the same language community and have a certain national character and consciousness. The linguistic representation of the world is the reality reflected in the language, the linguistic division of the world, information about the world,

¹⁹¹ <https://daryo.uz/en/2023/03/23/uzbekistan-ranks-second-in-number-of-telegram-channels>.

¹⁹² Andreas M. Kaplan *, Michael Haenlein, Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media, 0007-6813/\$ — see front matter # 2009 Kelley School of Business, Indiana University. All rights reserved. doi:10.1016/j.bushor.2009.09.003

transmitted using language units of different levels. First of all, you can look at the language picture of the world on Facebook and Twitter in the news section of social networks, where there is also a block "Active topics" that displays the most popular hashtags on the site. Hashtag (label) or hash - tag (eng. hashtag from hash) - "grid" symbol + tag). A word or phrase that precedes a given symbol. Users can group posts by topic or type using hashtags - words or phrases starting with #. The service allows users to track relevant topics and also helps users and the media understand the current agenda and issues of public concern at the moment. How quickly the current topics change on Facebook and Twitter shows that the language landscape of the world of social networks is very dynamic, it determines the attitude of a person to the world, his interest and participation in the events happening not only in his life. Recently, so-called public things occupy a special place in self-presentation of a person and reflection of his picture of the world. Public is a type of community created as a simplified version of a group, where the main goal is to convey interesting information to the subscriber as quickly and concisely as possible. A meme is a unit of cultural information. A meme can be any idea, symbol, style or method of action that is consciously or unconsciously transmitted from person to person through speech, writing, video, rituals, gestures, etc. Internet memes are information (links, text, images, even conversational structures) that are usually transmitted by users directly to each other over a network. This is usually done for entertainment purposes, but other information, including information of a provocative or harmful nature, may be distributed in the same way. Lexical units used in social networks play a special role in the formation of a unique network picture of the world, not in the meanings typical for them in ordinary speech. Determining qualitative changes in the semantic structure of words in their historical evolution is one of the main tasks of modern lexicology. The lexical units describing the communication within are accepted in the social network or network communication, they are actively changed (that is, they expand) their semantics and relevance. Within this phenomenon, within the framework of social network communication, first of all, it is determined by the semantics English and secondly, the influence of technical factors, interface features and functionality of the social network. In particular, this is already indicated by the names of the site's user menu links. Facebook and Twitter: "Home" (my page), "Groups" (groups / public), "News feed" (My news), "Saved" (My bookmarks), "Notification" (My replies), "Do list of friends" (My friends), "Followers" (subscribers), "Followers" m (subscriptions), "Tweets" (tweets / posts), "Trends" (thematic news) and others. A social network user is his own, "network" image of the world. It turns out that people outside of social networks are removed from the context of communication in them, they are not adapted. busy with new linguo-stylistic features of the language, they are not familiar with memes, abbreviations which are popular in other circles of users and therefore sometimes have difficulty understanding the interlocutor. People who are familiar with social communication and those who are not are two fundamentally different

types of communicators, even if the networks belong to the same generation or the same social class. Currently, the influence of social networks on live English speech is so great that researchers are opening new perspectives for the study of this area, and one of the most important directions (including from the point of view of lexicographic description of the language) is the study of the dynamics and causes of semantic changes. Many words are now given completely new meanings in the online context, which is used during verbal communication. Many words have been coined within the vast confines of the World Wide Web and have gained enough influence and prestige to be officially included in the Oxford Dictionary. A few of these words-selfie, inbox, noob, phablet, derp, photobomb, sext, and OMG-are so common in everyday conversation that we mention the new words alongside the old ones. They are also creeping into our spoken conversations. Research shows that while people prefer to use minimally relevant messages, almost a third of the modern generation tend to use rich vocabulary both on social networks and in formal letters, which expands the field of their technical knowledge. Because language has changed due to the influence of Internet communication, you may find that different people have different approaches to writing and speaking, as well as the way they communicate. With this, the language becomes more personalized and individual: this can be seen in every Twitter, in every profile. English is really changing, perhaps because it adapts easily and quickly, unlike other languages: since English has few inflections, nouns and adjectives easily turn into verbs like "About Google" - "google". English has adapted extremely easily to the faster and more diverse channels of communication in social networks and social technologies. Native speakers not only create and assimilate new language forms, but also popularize them. So abbreviations like LOL = 1) laugh out loud: 2) League of Legends is a free online game and BFF ("Best Friends Forever" or "Big Fat Friend/Female") becomes part of other languages. Research shows that abbreviations such as LOL or ROFL (Rolling On Floor Laughing) are widely used by many people. Today, Twitter and other popular social networks on the Internet posted all the new variations and forms of words. Before the advent of new social technologies, the main means of mass communication were newspapers, radio and television.

DISCUSSION. The process of interaction between people in social networks is a whole ritual that takes place within the framework of its own rules and laws. They are out of voice and are more likely to simplify establishing contact and reduce writing time than to neglect established language norms. To better understand the changes in the English language under the influence of social networks, theoretical fundamental knowledge in the field of communications was studied. Firstly, the characteristics of the main means of communication were studied, namely, the definition of communication, its social meaning, the sides of this process, the main components and ways of transmitting information were considered. The structure of communication and the components of speech activity were also studied. Secondly, a thorough analysis of the specifics of the language of social networks was carried out. Its main

features are mass character, mediation, an increase in the number of forced contacts, a contradiction between the form, means of communication and its content, as well as the active growth of quasi-communication. For a more complete and in-depth study of the characteristics of the English language in social networks, changes in the main sections of linguistics were considered: morphology, vocabulary and syntax. Based on the examples given in the WRC text, it can be concluded that the changes affected all sections under consideration. On the part of morphology, the changes affected the composition of the word: users of social networks lengthen words by repeating the same letter in roots and suffixes or, conversely, tame them with the help of abbreviations, and also give great preference to interjections and a complete change in the composition of a word without changing its meaning. If we consider the changes in the English language from the side of vocabulary, we can say that many words remain unchanged in terms of spelling, but completely change their meaning. So a surname can be a verb, and a verb can be a noun. The vocabulary of the English language when communicating on social networks is quite free: users use profanity and jargon when communicating in comments. The syntax of the English language has also undergone changes, which are expressed in simplifying the rules for writing sentences. A clearly established word order fades into the background, punctuation is simplified. Emoji users on social media can understand each other when conveying a message. Emoji continue to be the social rules traditionally co-developed by users in social networks (WA). Thus, text in social networks (WA) is built on the basis of verbal and non-verbal language elements (emoji). The emoji function strengthens the meaning and social connections between users in communication.

Findings from the texts show that people use all forms of non-traditional language codes or writing systems and ignore or disregard context and their combined effects. Such linguistic abysmal nature and pedagogic deviation of the language of social networks poses a great threat to the government, social and educational sectors. It urges the public to use the innovation of social networks with caution. This is true when we remember that the development, change and maintenance of our world and environment depend to a large extent on the communicative power of language and the pedagogical potential of young people.

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